

Static Hand Gesture Based Human Computer Interaction Using Convolution Neural Network

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Abstract

Human computer interaction is a hot topic among researchers primarily due to its application in healthcare, intelligent homes and helping people with disabilities. Through this paper we aim to propose a solution to bridge the gap between the computer and human. The proposed solution uses static gestures selected from the American sign language (ASL) and uses artificial neural network(Alex net). We were able to achieve an accuracy of 95% with our dataset of more than 30,000 images split into train and test images in the ratio 20:1.

1. Introduction

Hand Gesture recognition has been a prominent topic of research to make applications more user-friendly and bridge the gap between human and computer [2]. There are three stages of recognition system :- early vision, pattern perception and inference[1]. Our gesture recognition system aims to be real-time, reliable and deployable subjected to inconsistent background lightings[4] and various gesture positions and angles[5]. This paper proposes a interaction system between humans and computer, where we are able to control the applications associated to a command using different gestures hence enabling us to control the computer[6][7]. For visual recognition systems, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) [11], [13], have emerged as reliable and robust method of classification. Recent research have shown that supervised learning has produced wonderful results in the field of object recognition system[12]. The pretrained network alexine, provided us with the impetus to start and implement transfer learning on it[9][15]. Training parameters such as initial learning rate, stochastic gradient, batch size play an important role in the performance of the trained network[14][16]. This paper also compares our approach with various approaches used earlier which are discussed in the section evaluation and discussion. Therefore, this paper presents a static hand gesture recognition system which uses deep learning for human computer interaction.

2. Human Computer Interaction

Human Gestures are more intuitive way to communicate with the computer. The use of hand gestures provides us an attractive and reliable technique for the insufficient interface devices for

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Human Computer Interaction (HCI). We use various hand gestures in order to express our feelings and thoughts [7]. However, it is hard to replicate human actions with computer output so we used American Sign Language as it is the most widespread sign language. We selected 9 gestures for HCI. We used vision-based gesture recognition with the use of webcam to capture gesture using bare hands . The interpretation of these hand gestures can help in achieving the ease and naturalness desired for Human Computer Interaction.

3. The Dataset

We aimed to create a robust dataset for our proposed solution so that it can handle variations such as different backgrounds and lightings. Images are captured from different angles to achieve higher accuracy. Our dataset comprised of 30000 images with each gesture contributing 3000 images. For the identification to be less complex we have taken images with high contrast and homogeneous background. The images are stored in different folders, each dedicated to a particular gesture functioning as label for training the network. We converted each image into [227,227,3] pixel format to fit into Alex Net required image size.

Fig 1. Images of Gestures in dataset

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4. Fine-tuning alexine

Alex net is a revolutionary network which achieved unprecedented accuracy and speed. It consists of 25 fully connected layers fulfilling various functions. We reduced the Alex net's 1000 classification labels to 10 classification labels for our desired system which reduced training time and increased accuracy considerably.

5. Implementation details

Supervised learning is a deep learning method which uses labeled data to train the network which results in accurate outputs. Classification problem There are basically two types of problem in deep learning i.e. Regression and Classification problem and Hand gesture recognition comes under Classification problem as the system classifies gestures. We used augmented image datastore to transform bunch of training and test data. We resize images to make them compatible with the input size of our deep learning network. We augment training image data with randomized preprocessing operations to prevent the CNN from overfitting and memorizing the exact details of the training images. The advantage of using augmented image datastore is that the datastore randomly changes the training dataset for each iteration, so that each iteration uses a slightly different dataset and the dataset in each iteration is not saved in memory. Initial learning rate is a training parameter which controls how much we are adjusting the weights of a network. If the learning rate is low, then training is more reliable, but optimization will take a lot of time.

$$\theta_{\ell+1} = \theta_{\ell} - \alpha \nabla E(\theta_{\ell})$$

where ℓ stands for the iteration number, $\alpha > 0$ is the learning rate, θ is the parameter vector, and $E(\theta)$ is the loss function. The gradient of the loss function, $\nabla E(\theta)$, is evaluated using the entire training set, and the standard gradient descent algorithm uses the entire dataset at once.

Fig.2 Epoch plot

6. Evaluation and Discussion

Data augmentation : Initially, when we did not use data augmentation it resulted in storage space problem and complications in handling large data in each iteration. It showed high accuracy of 95% which works pretty good in detecting and recognizing the gestures.

Effects of background : The gesture images with non-homogeneous background and low contrast affects accuracy and ability to process gestures decreases/falters. It arises fluctuations while determining gesture.

Comparison with segmented image based classification: Segmented images take large amount of storage space which leads to unintended lag in the system performance. It also shows less accuracy to overcome that it, require complex mathematical equation which further leads to delay in the processing.

Fig. 3 Segmented image

The training time required to train the Alex net using transfer learning was 5-6 hrs (no parallel processing).

The system configurations are:

Graphics card -2GB NVIDIA GeForce 940M Processor - Intel i5-5200U

Ram - 8GB

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Fig. 4 Alex net transfer learning

7. Conclusion and future scope

This paper presents a accurate approach at hand gesture recognition for HCI applications with a classification rate accuracy of 95%. Our current implementation uses a set of 9 gestures. The results shows that our vision based gesture recognition system can be effectively used for HCI and robots, even for small applications. We plan to enhance this application by increasing the number of gestures and train the system with the increased dataset and enhanced feature extraction.

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